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Review Article

ANTIBIOTIC PRESCRIBING QUALITY FOR CHILDREN IN PRIMARY CARE A REVIEW

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Abstract:

Aim: To understand the factors influencing parental attitudes towards antibiotic prescribing.

Background: Overuse of antibiotics and inappropriate prescribing has resulted in rapid development of antimicrobial resistance (AMR), and is significant global threat to patient safety. In Primary Care settings, substantial numbers of antibiotics are prescribed for young children, despite viral nature of illness for which antibiotics are ineffective. Parents, play a vital role in decision making regarding accessing healthcare services and requesting treatment for their children.

Design: A systematic review was conducted in alignment with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses (PRISMA) statement (Moher et al 2015).

Methods: The CINAHL, MEDLINE, PsycINFO, The Cochrane Library, BRITISH NURSING INDEX, EMBASE and PUBMED databases were searched for primary research published between 2006-16. All types of primary research were searched and screened against inclusion criteria. The Critical Appraisal Skills Programme tool was used to appraise identified publications.

Quantitative data was summarised descriptively and qualitative data was thematically analysed.

Results: A total of 515 publications were initially screened, and 55 full-text articles were eligibility assessed. Twenty papers met inclusion criteria. Four main themes were identified: the quality of relationships with health care providers, dealing with conflicting messages, rationalising antibiotic use and parental practices informed by past experience.

Conclusion: Parents wanted reassurance and advice regarding children's illnesses, had poor antibiotic knowledge and were influenced by personal past experiences. More accessible education, including simple information leaflets, is required. Further research on the influence of culture, ethnicity and socio-economic factors would be beneficial.

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INTRODUCTION:

The use of antibiotics is a core and integrated component in modern healthcare (Department of Health 2013; Chief Medical Officer Report 2011). However, the global, widespread use of antibiotics in healthcare, animal health and food production, has led to a serious overuse and abuse of antibiotics. As a result, there has been an emergence of a phenomenon called antimicrobial resistance (AMR); defined as a microorganism's resistance to an antimicrobial drug to which it was once effective (World Health Organisation 2016). AMR is developing faster than new strains of antibiotics are being developed. Very few new antibiotics have reached the market in the last 30 years, (Parliamentary Science and Technology Committee 2014) primarily due to difficulties demonstrating their efficacy or because of unacceptable side effects such as nausea and vomiting. In addition, the poor financial return associated with antibiotic development and licensing does little to incentivise pharmaceutical companies to focus their resources on this activity (Sukkar 2013).

AMR is considered to be one of the most significant threats to patient safety worldwide (HM Government 2016, Johnstone 2016). Resistance to antibiotics makes procedures such as minor surgery and routine operations high-risk, increasing the duration of illness and leading to premature mortality (Chief Medical Officer Report 2011; HM Government 2016). A review on AMR published in 2016 found that currently 700,000 people die each year due to resistant infections and it is estimated that by 2050 the world will face an additional 10 million deaths due to AMR infections at a cost of \$100 trillion to the global economy (HM Government 2016). In response to the threat of AMR, the UK government has published the Five Year Antimicrobial Resistance Strategy 2013 to 2018 (Department of Health 2013). This strategy includes key actions to improve the knowledge and understanding of AMR, including the provision of better information for the general public, improved global surveillance of drug resistance and antimicrobial consumption in humans and animals,

and the development of more effective early warning systems to improve health outcomes.

The strategy also sets out to conserve and steward the effectiveness of existing antibiotic treatments and stimulate the development of new ones (Department of Health 2013). Research indicates doctors are the primary prescribers of antibiotics in the community and prescribe more often than clinically necessary. A substantial number of patients fail to complete a full course of antibiotics, as their symptoms improve, sometimes saving tablets for later self-medication (McNulty et al 2013). Failure to complete a course of antibiotics could allow microorganisms to recover and develop resistance to the antibiotic, affecting future efficacy (Davies and Davies 2010). In addition, some patients believe that antibiotics are effective against viruses (McNulty et al 2007), and some evidence from the Parliamentary Science and Technology Committee (2014), indicates considerable pressure from patients on clinicians to prescribe antibiotics, as well as poor public awareness of AMR and the potential risks associated with increasing AMR. In 2015, Public Health England (PHE) published the second annual report from the English Surveillance Programme for Antimicrobial Utilisation and Resistance (ESPAUR), which showed that, in 2014, the majority of antibiotics in England were prescribed in general practice (74%). Total antibiotic prescribing, which is measured using defined daily doses (DDD), a standardised measure of antibiotic consumption, continues to increase in the National Health Service (NHS) by 6.2% (16.1 to 17.1 DDD per 1000 inhabitants) between 2011 and 2014 and 2.1% between 2013 and 2014. However, this increase was at a slower rate in 2013 - 2014. The total number of prescriptions dispensed has decreased, whilst total antibiotic consumption in primary care has increased. This suggests higher doses or longer course lengths in general practice prescriptions. Antibiotics are prescribed in about one in five general practitioner (GP) consultations, with about 25% being prescribed to children between the ages of one and fourteen years (Murphy et al 2012). However, most childhood illnesses are caused by viruses rather than bacteria (Murphy et al 2012) often spontaneously resolving

without medical intervention, as in the case of the common cold or in childhood illnesses such as chickenpox. Clinicians report parents' apply pressure for antibiotics to be prescribed, mostly on behalf of their children (Stivers 2002).

However, inappropriate prescribing of antibiotics by clinicians can reinforce the belief that antibiotics ought to be prescribed and are effective in circumstances when they are not (Mangione -Smith et al 2006). Therefore, the need to educate both clinicians and parents, as the primary care givers, regarding the appropriate use of antibiotics is vital in safeguarding existing, effective antibiotics for the future. Aim and research questions The aim of the review was to examine the literature to explore any influences on parental attitudes to antibiotic prescribing and aimed to answer the following research questions: • What factors influence parental attitudes and expectations in relation to antibiotic prescribing for their children; and, • To what extent do social factors such as parental age, socio-economic groups, ethnicity, family cultures, beliefs and cultural background, influence parental attitudes .

METHODS:

Design:

A systematic approach to literature searching was used. The CINAHL, MEDLINE, PsycINFO, The Cochrane Library , BRITISH NURSING INDEX, EMBASE and PUBMED databases were searched for primary research published between 2006 -16, relating to the research question and using the identified search terms: parent, mother, maternal, beliefs, attitudes, antibiotics, child, primary care, general practice viral illness.

Search methods:

The review included all relevant published research conducted worldwide between the years 2006 - 2016 exploring knowledge, attitudes and practices of parents regarding use of antibiotics in primary care for their children. Searches were limited to the last ten years due to significant changes and increased recognition of the risk of antibiotic overuse in this time. Studies before this may not reflect current practices or knowledge. All publications, including cohort studies, randomised controlled trials (RC T s), and both observational studies and qualitative studies were eligible. Only primary research studies which were published in English were eligible for inclusion. Grey literature was searched and included Department of Health, World Health Organisation, HM Government, Centre for Disease Control, Royal Pharmaceutical Society, Royal College of General

Practitioners and Public Health England literature. Additional searches were conducted using Google Scholar to identify any other relevant or unpublished studies. An additional hand search was conducted of the identified article references to ensure relevant studies were not missed and maximum relevant articles were obtained (Aveyard 2014).

RESULTS:

Thematic analysis of the papers identified four main themes from the literature review. These were 'quality of relationships with health care providers', 'dealing with conflicting messages', 'rationalising the need for antibiotics', and 'parental practices informed by past experience'. Quality of relationships with health care providers Eleven of the studies identified the importance of relationship quality between parents and clinicians. These studies found parents were concerned and anxious for their child's health and wanted to be reassured regarding the decision making and care their clinicians provide d (Al -Dossari 2013, Alili -Idrizi et al 2014, Alkhaldi et al 2015, Brookes -Howell et al 2013, Cabral et al 2016, Chinnasami et al 2016, Ecker et al 2013, Panagakou et al 2011, Rousounidis et al 2011, Salazar et al 2012, Zyoud et al 2015). The relationship quality between the parent/clinician was founded on trust. In half the studies , trust was more likely to develop if parents experienced open communication. This involved easy clinician access, and using a range of communication methods (telephone, email, appointments) which enabled relationship building (Al -Dossari 2013, Alkhaldi et al 2015, Brookes -Howell et al 2013, , Chinnasami et al 2016, Ecker et al 2013, Finkelstein et al 2013, Panagakou, et al 2011, Rousounidis et al 2011, Vaz et al 2015, Zyoud et al 2015). The importance of communication was identified in ten studies, which recognised parent s relied on their clinicians for advice and information on their child's treatment options. This clinician engagement enabled parents to feel supported in their decision making and resulted in feelings of general satisfaction with the amount of information they were given regarding the need for antibiotics and the risks involved (Al -Dossari 2013, Alkhaldi et al 2015, Brookes -Howell et al 2013, Cabral et al 2016, Chinnasami et al 2016, Ecker et al 2013, Panagakou et al 2011, Rousounidis et al 2011, Salazar et al 2012, Zyoud et al 2015). However, in seven studies, parents did not experience good communication with their clinicians, as they felt clinicians used complex language, did not explain the terms they used and did not spend enough time providing explanations (Agarwal et al 2015, Alkhaldi et al 2015, Cabral et al 2016, Chinnasami et al 2016, Dwibedi et al 2015, Ecker 2013, Wun et al 2012).

Three studies identified a lack of time as contributing to poor explanations of the rationale for decision making and antibiotic side effect profiles (Alkhalidi et al 2015, Ecker et al 2013, Wun, et al 2012); this led to parents not understanding why treatments were being offered or when antibiotics should be used. As a result, parents felt ill-informed regarding the care of their child (Agarwal et al 2015, Al Dossari 2013, Alkhalidi et al 2015). Eleven studies identified that in private healthcare systems, regular follow ups with clinicians either by phone or home/office visit, were more common. Parents reported more satisfaction when they knew and trusted their clinician and felt the clinician knew their family (Al -Dossari 2013, Alili -Idrizi et al 2014, Alkhalidi et al 2015, Brookes -Howell et al 2013, Cabral et al 2016, Chinnasami et al 2016, Ecker et al 2013, Panagakou et al 2011, Rousounidis et al 2011, Salazar et al 2012, Zyoud et al 2015).

DISCUSSIONS:

Nearly three quarters of the studies identified discrepancies in the perception of parents and clinicians regarding the expectation of receiving antibiotics (Al -Dossari 2013, Alili -Idrizi et al 2014, Cabral et al 2016, Chan and Tang 2006, Chinnasami et al 2016, Farha et al 2016, Finkelstein et al 2013, Panagakou et al 2011, Rousounidis et al 2011, Salazar et al 2012, Salonga 2009, Wun et al 2012, Yu et al 2014, Zyoud et al 2015). In one study, 28% of parents reported they directly requested antibiotics from their clinician. This was in contrast to 60% of clinicians who reported feeling directly pressurised by parents to prescribe antibiotics, which they expected to receive even when not clinically indicated (Rousounidis et al 2011). The familiarity and relationship with the clinician may have influenced mothers to ask for and receive antibiotics. Six studies found parent's attitudes and beliefs are influenced by anxiety and concern for their child's welfare (Alkhalidi et al 2015, Brookes -Howell et al 2013, Cabral et al 2016, Dwibedi et al 2015, Ecker et al 2013, Finkelstein et al 2013). This concern resulted in seeking clinician advice. However, if the advice resulted in antibiotic prescribing, the perception of the seriousness of the child's illness and antibiotic need was reinforced (Alili -Idrizi et al 2014, Rousounidis et al 2011). Two other studies identified that if a child had received antibiotics in the past for a similar illness, parents expected an antibiotic prescription would be provided again. When parents did receive antibiotics it reinforced belief in their decision making (Cabral et al 2016, Ecker et al 2013). Three studies cited the rationalising of antibiotic usage to prevent child illness (Al -Dossari 2013, Alkhalidi et al 2015, Yu et al 2014). In one study, nearly half of parents believed antibiotics could

protect children from common colds and therefore they were more likely to give antibiotics prophylactically (Yu et al 2014). Only two studies identified that parents recognised antibiotics should be kept for more serious illnesses (Cabral et al 2016, Chan and Tang 2006). Six studies identified that parents believed antibiotics could treat all manner of infections, were considered 'wonder' drugs and in limitless supply as new antibiotics were always being developed (Chan and Tang 2006, Ecker et al 2013, Panagakou et al 2011, Rousounidis et al 2011, Yu et al 2014, Zyoud et al 2015). The culture of parents, which includes the ideas, customs, and social behaviour, was identified in five studies to influence antibiotic usage (Alkhalidi et al 2015, Chan and Tang 2006, Panagakou et al 2011, Salazar et al 2012, Salonga 2009)

CONCLUSION:

The review identified the main themes that impact on and influence parental expectations to receive antibiotics for their children. One main influence was the concern and the perceived seriousness of their child's illness. Parents relied on the clinician to provide reassurance, advice and information regarding the care of their child; however lack of consultation time and use of complex language impacted on the quality of parents and clinicians relationship. As a result, parents were not reassured and often relied on previous experiences and outcomes that had influenced their expectations. The literature identified a gap in qualitative studies to explore the knowledge, attitudes and practices of parents. Further high quality research should be undertaken to explore the underlying issues experienced by parents. This will enable parents to gain a deeper understanding of appropriate antibiotic use and where to obtain information, potentially influencing future behaviour. Suitable strategies and interventions need to be developed, to address these influences and accessible information provided to parents, so they can make informed decisions regarding their child's health.

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